

Precise fertilization in greenhouse crops using modern decision support systems to save fertilisers and mitigate pollution of water resources

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Abstract

Inappropriate fertilisation and farming practices result in serious environmental impacts. These include overloading of soils with nutrients, which may result in pollution of groundwater with nitrates and phosphates, eutrophication in surface water, air pollution due to emission of greenhouse gasses and ammonia, rainfall acidification, and unwanted N-deposition in natural environments, harming thereby the whole ecosystem. To address these problems, there is an urgent need to apply new agricultural production approaches and innovative technologies for crop management targeting the reduction of inputs and the circularity of resources. ECONUTRI is an Innovation Action project funded by the European Commission (Horizon Europe), which is based on a multi-actor approach and aims at minimising or even eliminating nitrogen and phosphorus pollution of water resources and saving fertilisers without compromising yield. To restrict NO₃ leaching and P runoff due to inappropriate fertilization practices, the rates and timing of application must be adjusted to crop requirements and soil types. To achieve this goal, researchers from The Netherlands, Spain and Greece are currently testing at farm scale three user-friendly DSSs aimed to plan precise nutrient management of basal applications and fertigation in soil-grown and soilless vegetable crops. The DSS prepared by the Agricultural University of Athens was obtained by further developing the software NUTRISENSE (<https://nutrisense.online/>) to create two versions, one used by soilless growers and a second one aiming to support soil-grown crops. The SOILLESS NUTRISENSE is used to calculate standard nutrient solutions for a diversity of soilless cultivated plants considering a water analysis, the season of the year and the plant developmental stage and readjusting their composition when a chemical analysis of the drainwater is available. The SOIL NUTRISENSE is used to precisely calculate fertiliser requirements for basal dressing and fertigation of diverse crop species, mostly open-field and greenhouse vegetables, considering the season, irrigation water quality and soil analysis.

Key Words: Econutri; fertigation; hydroponics; nitrate pollution, nutrient model, soilless culture

1. INTRODUCTION

An appreciable part of the yearly N supply in agriculture is lost, with estimates of up to 107 kg/ha in Europe (Zhang et al., 2016). Losses of N occur either in mineral form due to leaching and run-off, or in gaseous form due to denitrification and ammonia volatilization. Both processes result in serious adverse effects on the environment. Furthermore, part of P supplied to the crops is lost through runoff to the surface water. Emissions of both N and P to surface water result in eutrophication, which is a serious environmental pollution concern (Conley et al., 2009). To

mitigate pollution of water resources caused by inappropriate fertilisation and irrigation practices, there is an urgent need to apply new agricultural production approaches and innovative technologies for crop management targeting the reduction of inputs as well as the circularity of resources. These actions are urgently needed to protect groundwater as a major source of drinking water and prevent pollution of surface waters including seas and oceans. Taking into consideration this challenge, the Green Deal of EU has set as a target a reduction of at least 20% in fertilizer use up to 2030 by improving the fertiliser use efficiency, thus achieving a reduction of nutrient losses by 50% to the benefit of both farmers and the environment (https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en).

To substantially reduce nutrient losses thus contributing to the control of environmental pollution originating from the application of organic and inorganic fertilisers, nature-based innovative technologies for both conventional and organic farming must be deployed. Examples of nature-based technologies to reduce pollution from fertiliser in agriculture are precise fertilization using remote sensing technologies (Balafoutis et al., 2017, van Evert et al., 2017), accurate calculation of plant nutrient needs using suitable algorithms integrated into dedicated computer programs (Garaldo et al., 2023, Savvas et al., 2023), variable rate application of manure/slurries (Basso et al., 2016), real-time sensing to recycle inorganic nutrients in soilless cropping systems (Giannothanasis et al., 2023), biostimulants and smart fertilizers contributing to an increase of the nutrient use efficiency (Kaloizoumis et al., 2021), etc. These technologies must be integrated into smart nutrient and irrigation management plans following efficient novel methodologies that should be based on a holistic concept.

3. CONTRIBUTION OF ECONUTRI TO SUSTAINABLE NUTRIENT MANAGEMENT

Recently, the European Commission approved the innovation project ECONUTRI, which aims to contribute to a substantial reduction of plant nutrient losses in Agriculture. ECONUTRI, coordinated by the Agricultural University of Athens, started on 1 November 2022 and is scheduled to last 42 months. The underpinning concept of ECONUTRI is to develop, apply and validate nature-based innovative solutions that effectively prevent mitigate and/or eliminate nutrient pollution of soils, water, and air. Following a holistic approach, ECONUTRI considers soil water and air as different components of the same organism, namely the ecosystem, and aims to address not only the impacts of single polluting sources but also their interactions and interconnections. The holistic approach considers a complex system (in ECONUTRI this is the nutrient cycle in agriculture) as a coherent whole that is also part of something greater. To assure a broad-spectrum coverage of the different components contributing to a holistic concept, ECONUTRI deploys 30 partner institutions from research, industry, and the farmer community. Twenty-one out of the thirty partners originate from 10 EU countries, one from Norway, two from UK, and 6 from China. To establish a holistic concept, ECONUTRI addresses pollution due to emissions arising from both crop fertilization and organic biomass waste, including biowaste sources from both animal and plant production. Avoidance of emissions through reduced biowaste production, less fertilizer application without compromising crop productivity and farmer viability, and appropriate control of the production procedures constitute the major components of the ECONUTRI's holistic approach.

Trapping, collecting, and ultimately recycling nutrient residues, specifically NO_3 and P or biomass rich in these components, either directly or for alternative uses, is another pillar of the holistic concept deployed by ECONUTRI. Finally, engaging all actors in the agri-food sector, the consumers, and society into the implementation of the nature-based solutions and technologies constitutes the third pillar necessary for the success of this holistic concept. Thus, ultimately, the

core of the ECONUTRI concept is the development of a circular agricultural production system, in which organic waste biomass is processed to recover plant nutrients and returned to the soil to support a sustainable production with minimal polluting emissions, towards a target of zero pollution. A schematic illustration of the holistic approach of ECONUTRI is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The holistic concept of ECONUTRI towards a sustainable nutrient management in agriculture aiming to keep N/P emissions within safe ecological boundaries towards a zero-pollution end-target.

The nature-based solutions deployed by ECONUTRI to control nutrient emissions in agriculture have been allocated into 24 appropriately selected innovative technologies, which address the most important pollution sources. The selection of the 24 innovative technologies has been based on both a holistic concept and an “application-oriented” approach. One of these innovative technologies is the use of specialty designed Decision Support Systems (DSS) to precisely calculate the amounts of fertilisers needed by each specific crop and provide advice about their application procedures. The current paper is mainly devoted to the application of DSS as means to restrict waste of plant nutrients in agriculture.

2. USE OF DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEMS TO OPTIMISE FERTIGATION OF VEGETABLES

Innovative DSS which incorporate the latest state of knowledge can substantially contribute to restriction of NO₃ leaching and P runoff due to inappropriate fertilization practices in agriculture and horticulture. Specialty designed DSS enable precise adjustments of the rates and timing of fertiliser application to crop requirements and soil types. Several DSS have been developed to support fertigation of vegetable crops based on modelling and prediction of nutrient uptake. Some of them aim at predicting nutrient requirements by simulating crop growth and plant biomass production, in combination with input data from regular determinations of tissue nutrient concentrations (Elia and Conversa, 2015; Gallardo et al., 2016, 2020, 2021; Ramírez-Pérez et al., 2018). Some other DSS are mainly based on estimations of the nutrient status in the root environment (soil or drainwater in soilless crops) and the changes recorded during the cropping period due to the uptake of nutrients by plants (Savvas, 2002; Massa et al., 2011; Moreira Barradas et al., 2018). Most of these DSS deploy models which either were developed to simulate nutrient uptake in crops grown on the soil (Conversa et al., 2015; Elia and Conversa, 2015), or can be used in both soil-grown and soilless crops (Gallardo et al., 2016, 2020, 2021). Only few DSS were specifically developed for soilless crops (Anastasiou et al., 2005, Massa et al., 2020, Savvas et al., 2020, 2021). However, there is hardly any report in peer-reviewed publications on DSS specifically designed to support the fertigation of crops cultivated in closed-loop soilless crops.

An additional problem with the use of DSS to support precise fertilisation in vegetable crops is that most of the available DSS are used either locally, or by private companies to support their clients. Consequently, the accessibility to credible DSS that could support growers in tailoring fertiliser supply to the plant needs, thus minimising nutrient losses and environmental pollution, is currently a challenge. Taking this into consideration, ECONUTRI has included in its workplan the development of three user-friendly DSSs to plan precise nutrient management through both basal fertiliser applications and fertigation in both soil-grown and soilless vegetable crops.

One DSS deployed by ECONUTRI to achieve its goals is the VegSyst-DSS which is based on prescriptive-corrective management of nutrition and irrigation of vegetable crops grown both in soil and on substrates and aims to reduce fertiliser application and nutrient loss (Gallardo et al., 2023). Prescriptive management is based on the adaptation of standard recommendations available in credible literature sources to soil analysis before crop establishment, while corrective management is based on plant sap testing, and analysis of soil and soil solution during the cropping period. This DSS will be validated and demonstrated at farm scale in Spain in collaboration with the growers' organisation COEXPHAL.

A second DSS designed by Dutch scientists will be used in the Netherlands to optimise irrigation and fertilisation management in soil-grown greenhouse crops under northern European cropping conditions. This DSS will make recommendations for fertiliser basal dressing, organic amendments, and daily fertigation to meet crop requirements and to minimise nutrient leaching. The novel Dutch DSS will combine the existing models 'FERTIGATIONMODEL' and 'WATERSTROMEN' with the recently developed 'VIRTUAL LYSIMETER' (van der Salm et al., 2020). A comprehensive mineralisation module for manure/organic materials will also be integrated, enabling the DSS to serve organic producers. This DSS will be implemented on a large scale by a growers' organisation in the Netherlands.

A third DSS will be obtained by further developing the software NUTRISSENSE which is mainly used by soilless growers (Savvas et al., 2021). The expanded NUTRISSENSE will consist of two versions, one for soil-grown crops (SOIL NUTRISSENSE) and a second one for soilless cultivation (SOILLESS NUTRISSENSE). The DSS NUTRISSENSE is presented below in more detail.

4. THE CONCEPT OF NUTRISENSE

NUTRISENSE is a software used for the computation of nutrient solutions (NS) destined to be applied for fertigation of soilless and soil-grown crops (Savvas et al., 2021). The currently available version of NUTRISENSE, which is accessible on-line on the internet at <https://nutrisense.online/>, is mainly designed to serve the soilless growers and the scientists who provide advisory services to soilless growers. However, currently, NUTRISENSE is further developed and extended to include a specialty designed version for soil-grown greenhouse crops. The two versions of NUTRISENSE are presented in sub-sections 4.1 and 4.2.

4.1. NUTRISENSE for soilless cultivations

4.1.1. The concept of plant nutrition in soilless cultivations

The roots of the plants are in contact with the root solution (RS) and thus, the satisfaction of their nutritional requirements depends directly on the nutrient status in the root environment, irrespective of whether they are grown in the soil or in soilless systems. In soil-grown crops, the nutrient status in the root environment depends on the quantity of the nutrient reserves and the rate at which they are released to the soil solution and can, therefore, not easily and quickly alter due to nutrient uptake and crop fertilisation practices. However, in soilless crops, the nutrient reserves are small due to the restricted volume of root zone per plant (Sonneveld 1981). Consequently, in soilless crops, the nutrient composition in the RS may exhibit considerable fluctuations within short periods of time. Thus, to ensure optimal nutrition in a soilless crop, the composition of the NS should be considered a variable that may change frequently, aiming to achieve the primary objective which is the maintenance of a target nutrient status in the root environment (Blok et al., 2023). Thus, the main objective of an efficient nutrient management system in soilless crops should be to maintain an optimal nutrient status in the root zone by properly modifying fertilization practices whenever needed to achieve this goal. In other words, the nutrient status in the root zone is the strategic target, while the rates of external nutrient supply via fertilization represent the tactics, which may be altered during the cropping period to achieve the strategic target. Applying this concept in soilless culture means that for each crop a target nutrient composition has to be maintained in the RS using the supplied solution (SS) as a tool. However, the composition of the SS may be modified whenever needed to achieve the target composition in the root zone. This concept was first introduced by Dutch scientists (Sonneveld and Straver, 1984; de Krijg et al., 1999; Sonneveld and Voogt 2009) and is referenced to as “Dutch nutrient recommendation system” (Blok et al., 2023).

ECONUTRI supports and promotes the expansion of closed-loop soilless culture systems (CLS) in greenhouse crops, aiming to eliminate emissions of NO_3 and P that normally occur in soil-grown and open soilless horticultural crops due to drainage of fertigation effluents. In CLS, the fertigation effluents, routinely termed drainage solution (DS), are collected and recycled, and thus pollution of water resources is avoided. Recycling of the DS is already applied in soilless-cultivated horticultural crops in north-European countries, such as The Netherlands. However, they are rarely applied in south-European countries because the relevant advisory services are weak and growers in most cases do not have the means to control the variability of nutrient concentrations in the DS. Thus, in most cases, they are not willing to collect and recycle the DS. About 30-35% of the NS supplied to open soilless cultivations is emitted into the environment. Collection and recycling of the DS can considerably restrict pollution of the aquifers with nitrates and phosphates, while also reducing fertiliser consumption. To support growers in switching to CLS, ECONUTRI deploys the DSS NUTRISENSE to accurately calculate NS formulas when the DS is recycled, thus harmonising the nutrient supply with the nutrient uptake by plants.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the process of nutrient solution preparation in open (1A) and closed-loop soilless cropping systems (1B) and the terminology used for the different parameters involved. **Water:** the raw water used for the preparation of NS; **Fertilisers:** liquid stock solutions of water-soluble fertilizers used to add nutrients to the NS; Plant **Uptake Concentrations (UC):** the ratios between each nutrient and the volume of water absorbed by the plant. **Drainage solution (DS):** the NS that drains out of the root zone after each irrigation event. **Supplied solution (SS):** the NS that is ultimately supplied to the crop, which in open SCS is a fresh NS prepared by mixing water with fertilisers, while in closed-loop SCS it is the mixture of nutrients, water, and DS. **Root solution (RS):** the NS that is in immediate contact with the plant roots. **Added solution (AS):** a NS with concentrations corresponding to the ratios between the net nutrient input and the net water input (thus excluding the input of DS), when preparing SS in CLS.

The nutrients provided via the supplied solution (SS) to a soilless cropping system are removed from the root environment either via plant uptake or via the drainage solution (Savvas and Gruda 2018; Blok et al., 2023). If the removal of nutrients from the system via these two paths is lower or higher than the supply, the excess or the missing nutrients will accumulate or deplete, respectively, in the root zone. Thus, to maintain optimal nutrient levels in the root zone, which is the strategic target, the nutrient supply should match the removal of nutrients via both paths of plant uptake and drainage. The output *via* drainage can be controlled by properly adjusting the drainage fraction. However, the nutrient uptake has to be estimated. Previous research has shown that for a standard nutrient status in the root zone, the nutrient to water uptake rates, frequently referred to as “uptake concentrations” in the international literature, fluctuate within a relatively narrow range under controlled greenhouse conditions. Thus, they can be used as reliable estimates of plant nutrient uptake. The experimental determination of mean uptake concentrations for a particular crop species is one of the two components needed to estimate optimal nutrient concentrations for this species in the SS. The second component is the determination of an optimal composition for the NS in the root zone (root solution) which is

generally very similar to that of the DS (Blok et al., 2023). Especially in closed-loop soilless cultivations, the uptake concentrations are directly applied as an added solution (AS), i.e., new NS prepared and mixed with drainwater to prepare the supplied solution. The above-referenced parameters, which are involved in the supply of NS to open and closed-loop soilless crops, as well as the relevant terminology, are schematically outlined in Figure 1.

4.1.2. Calculation of nutrient solutions using NUTRISENSE

The version of NUTRISENSE, that is currently available on-line on the internet at <https://nutrisense.online/>, has been designed for use mainly in open and closed-loop SCSs, although it can be used also in soil-grown crops. This version of NUTRISENSE is used to calculate NSs based on desired characteristics given as target values and readjust their composition during the cropping period after chemical analyses of the RS or the DS. NUTRISENSE utilises standard recommendations originating from various literature sources concerning the nutrient requirements of a wide variety of vegetable and ornamental plant species, which are available in a database (e.g., de Kreij et al., 1999; Neocleous and Savvas, 2013, 2015, 2018; Neocleous et al., 2021; Ropokis et al., 2021; Savvas et al., 2013, 2014, 2017; Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009; van der Lugt et al., 2020). The data from the various sources that was considered credible has been properly organised in the database of NUTRISENSE. When NUTRISENSE is used to compute a NS for a particular crop, the recommendations included in the database are adapted to the specific characteristics and conditions of this crop. More specifically, NUTRISENSE takes into consideration mainly the following crop characteristics when a NS formula is requested for a crop:

- crop species,
- season of the year,
- plant developmental stage,
- mineral composition of the raw water used to prepare the NS,
- available fertilisers,
- number and the volume of stock solution tanks
- specific characteristics of the available equipment for fertigation.

The core of NUTRISENSE is an extended version of the algorithm proposed by Savvas and Adamidis (1999, 2000). However, the current version incorporates many additional elements conferring extensive capabilities, as described in three recent papers (Savvas and Gruda, 2018; Savvas et al., 2020; Savvas et al., 2023a). One of the most important components included in this software to feed the extended version of the algorithm initially developed by Savvas and Adamidis (1999, 2000) is a database with standard NS compositions for different crop species, developmental stages (e.g., vegetative, or reproductive) and soilless culture systems (open or closed). This database includes a complete set of data for all important greenhouse crops, originating mainly from several literature sources (see Savvas and Neocleous, 2019, Savvas et al., 2023a and publications therein). Another novel component of NUTRISENSE is an algorithm used to automatically readjust the composition of the currently used NS after introduction of the DS composition to the software (Savvas et al., 2023a).

The available options regarding the type of NS to be calculated by NUTRISENSE are:

- starter solution (used to moisten the substrates or to fill up the tanks in water culture systems before planting),
- standard NS for an open hydroponic system,
- standard NS for a closed hydroponic system,
- readjusting the NS composition in an open hydroponic system,
- readjusting the NS composition in a closed hydroponic system.

If the selected type of NS is “adjusting the NS” (both in open and closed systems), the user has also to introduce the composition of the currently used NS and the current composition of the DS as determined through a recent chemical analysis. To maximize the benefits from a NS readjustment via NUTRISENSE, the time between collection of a DS sample and application of the readjusted NS formula should be as short as possible.

Figure 3. Schematic outline of the calculation and the adjustment of AS in a closed-loop SCS via DSS NUTRISENSE for soilless culture. The input data to DSS are the plant developmental stage, the mineral composition of the irrigation water, the chemical analysis of the DS and the climatic conditions. The output of DSS is the actual UC which are used to calculate also the proper AS and SS compositions that are applied to the crop via the fertigation system.

After introduction of this information to the NUTRISENSE portal, the user only has to request calculation of a new NS formula by clicking on “calculate NS formula” and the software provides immediately a full set of recommendations as output. The major components of this output are: i) the composition of the calculated NS, particularly EC, pH nutrient concentrations (mmol L^{-1}) and molar mutual ratios, and ii) full instructions about the preparation of SSs and their injection to water in the fertigation system used to prepare the final NS supplied to the crop. The molar ratios in the NS calculated by NUTRISENSE are K:Ca:Mg, N/K and $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}/\text{total-N}$.

It is important to note that in open SCSs the calculated NS is the SS, while in CLSs the calculated NS is the AS, provided that the nutrition of the crop is not controlled using ISEs. However, in CLSs operated with ISEs, the NS calculated by NUTRISENSE is the SS.

If the fertigation system works by diluting two concentrated solutions of and a concentrated solution of an acid for pH adjustment (A/B FS), while the DS is not recycled, NUTRISENSE calculates the exact masses of fertilizers to be added to the specified volume of water to prepare CSs. If an A/B FS is used in a CLS, NUTRISENSE calculates not only the masses of fertilizers needed to prepare CSs but also the EC of the solution obtained when the recycled DS is mixed with irrigation water. If a multi-tank fertigation system is used (a separate stock solution for each fertilizer), NUTRISENSE calculates the relative injection ratio of each fertilizer, which has to be introduced to the controlling system of the FS. Furthermore, NUTRISENSE can be additionally used to specify the optimal masses of fertilizer needed to prepare each individual CS, thereby contributing to a more accurate injection of all CSs to water when fresh NS is prepared.

4.2. Readjusting a NS formula using NUTRISENSE

The standard recommendations found in literature sources concerning the optimal composition of the SS or the AS are considered general estimations of the true nutrient requirements of a crop species. However, the exact nutrient requirements of a particular crop are rarely identical with those suggested in the literature because different crops grow under different conditions. Even small deviations between the standard recommendations and the true nutrient requirements of the plants are additive over time and may result in substantial nutrient imbalances. To avoid the occurrence of nutrient imbalances in the RS, the composition of the SS in open systems, or the AS in CLSs, is frequently readjusted to meet more precisely the actual plant uptake rates. To achieve this goal, a NS sample is collected frequently (i.e., fortnightly) either from the RS or from the DS and its mineral composition is determined through analytical procedures in a credible chemical laboratory. The results of the chemical analysis are immediately introduced to NUTRISENSE which is then prompted to provide a readjusted composition of the NS formula.

To readjust the composition of the AS supplied to a CLS, NUTRISENSE uses a novel algorithm based on mass balance equations. This algorithm calculates the actual UCs of the crop for an interval between two consecutive chemical analyses of the DS (Savvas et al., 2023a). The UC of each individual nutrient is calculated by taking into consideration: a) the difference in the mass of each individual nutrient in the RS-DS at the beginning and the end of the interval, and b) the added mass of this nutrient via the AS during this interval. Subsequently, NUTRISENSE calculates a readjusted AS composition (EC, pH and nutrient concentrations) assuming that the UCs estimated for the previous time interval are valid also for the next time interval. Any discrepancies will be compensated in the next readjustment of the AS. The readjusted formula of AS includes the target EC, pH and nutrient concentrations, as well as the masses of fertilisers needed to prepare the CSs, or the injection rates of each CS when single fertiliser CSs are used (Savvas and Gruda, 2018). A schematic representation of the algorithm used to readjust the AS in CLS is presented in Figure 3.

4.2. NUTRISENSE for soil-grown crops

In soil-grown greenhouse crops, part of the nutrients required by the plants is applied as a base-dressing. This is particularly the case with P (Sonneveld, 1995), which is rather immobile in the soil. In contrast, nitrogen, which is highly soluble in water as nitrate and ammonium salts, is supplied to the crop after planting through the irrigation system. This operation, which is widely known as fertigation, saves time, labour, and resources while maintaining or even improving crop yields. As a result, the water use efficiency increases considerably, provided that the dosages of both water and nutrients are properly assigned. The use of suitable dosing pumps or injectors enabling the maintenance of optimal nutrient concentrations in the irrigation water supplied to

the crop is a prerequisite for balanced plant nutrition. Nevertheless, the “optimal nutrient concentrations” need to be adjusted and specialized for each particular greenhouse crop species.

In many parts of the world, including most Mediterranean countries, many greenhouse growers still determine fertilizer application rates by a “rule of thumb”. In most cases, this practice results in excessive application rates of nitrogen, phosphorus and, less frequently, potassium. In some cases, excessive application of one or more nutrients is accompanied by an inadequate supply of other nutrients, thereby exacerbating the incidence of single nutrient toxicities or deficiencies, or even resulting in multi-nutritional disorders. To prevent such problems, balanced fertilization schemes based on knowledge of plant nutrient requirements and soil nutrient reserves, as determined by chemical soil analysis, are needed. Hence, optimal fertilizer application rates for each nutrient can be estimated by deducting the soil reserves from the total plant requirements. However, the practical application of this concept by growers is not a simple issue. A major difficulty arises from the many methods and concepts used to estimate the levels of available plant nutrients in the soil. Another problem is that even the most credible and accurate soil analysis data need interpretation and conversion into quantitative recommendations in the form of target nutrient concentrations in the fertigation solution.

Figure 4. Schematic outline of the calculation of the proper fertigation for a soil-grown crop via DSS NUTRISENSE. The input data to DSS are the soil analysis, the plant developmental stage, the mineral composition of the irrigation water, the plant nutrient status, and the climatic conditions. The output of DSS is the fertigation formula which is applied to the crop via the fertigation system.

The classical approach for estimating plant nutrient availability in the soil is the determination of exchangeable nutrient cations, which is based on the use of acetic acid and DTPA solutions for the extraction of plant available macro- and micro-cations, respectively (Gianquinto et al., 2013). Critical levels of exchangeable cations in greenhouse soils are given in Table 1 based on experience and standard laboratory practices. However, the determination of exchangeable cations is laborious and time consuming, since it requires the drying of soil samples. Furthermore, this method is restricted only to cations, while the determination of essential nutrients occurring as anions (P, N) or uncharged compounds (B) requires other procedures, for example, the Olsen method which is routinely used to estimate the plant available P in Mediterranean soils (Olsen and Sommers, 1982). Another approach that has been standardized in the Netherlands over the last decades is the determination of water-soluble nutrients in water extracts (de Bos et al., 1999). According to this method, the water-soluble nutrients contained in the soil are determined in 1:2 (soil to water in v/v) extracts (Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009). This method enables rapid estimation of the soil nutrient status because the samples do not require drying before the extraction process. However, a drawback of this method is that the measured concentrations do not reflect the actual nutrient levels in the soil solution due to variations in soil texture. Therefore, an accurate interpretation of results obtained for a specific soil type with this method is possible only after testing and adaptation to the current soil type.

The use of a DSS after a soil analysis to precisely formulate NS for soil-grown crops similar to those applied in soilless culture will considerably restrict overfertilization and thus soil and water pollution with N and P. Moreover, optimizing the nutrient management of soil-grown crops helps the economic sustainability of the growers due to higher yield production and reduced fertiliser consumption. A lower synthetic fertiliser input will also lead to energy saving from the fertiliser industry, thereby reducing CO₂ emissions.

DSS NUTRISENSE, which currently supports soilless growers, will be further developed as DSS NUTRISENSE SOIL for irrigated soil-grown horticultural crops. The DSS NUTRISENSE SOIL will precisely calculate fertiliser requirements for basal dressing and fertigation of diverse crop species, mostly open-field and greenhouse vegetables. The further development of NUTRISENSE, will match the special needs of soil-grown crops and optimize fertilizer application rates. This DSS will be used to precisely calculate the amounts of fertilisers needed to prepare an NS using a wide arrow of water-soluble fertilizers, for the fertigation of a particular crop species. Apart from the crop species, the calculations will take into consideration a soil analysis, the mineral composition of the irrigation water, the season of the year, and the plant developmental stage. Furthermore, SOIL NUTRISENSE would be able to adjust the fertigation via irrigation using data from a soil analysis, and plant nutrient status during the cultivation period. The SOIL NUTRISENSE DSS will be developed, tested, and experimentally validated in greenhouse facilities of stakeholders in a Mediterranean environment, who will receive full access and support within the framework of ECONUTRI to apply it at a commercial scale.

5. OUTLOOK

NUTRISENSE DSS is going to be further developed in the framework of ECONUTRI, a Horizon Europe innovation project, funded by the European Commission. One of the planned developments is a new version of DSS for real-time monitoring of nutrient supply, using ion selective electrodes (ISE) measurements of DS composition. The unknown DS composition due to unknown plant uptakes is a serious problem in soilless culture systems (SCS), especially in closed-loop systems, in which the DS is recycled. ISEs have an ion-selective membrane that responds selectively to one ion in multi-ion solutions such as a DS (Kim et al., 2013). Furthermore,

ISEs are practical tools with simple use, wide measurement range, and rapid and direct measurements (Cho et al., 2019; Peña-Fleitas et al., 2022). New ISE systems are fully automated with features such as auto-sampling and auto-calibration. The aim of this new version of NUTRISENSE is the online connection between automated ISE systems and fertigation systems for real time management of the NS composition. NUTRISENSE will also give the option for manual introduction of ISE measurements when portable ISE systems are used. Another aim is the inclusion, as an input for the DSS, data for the nutrient status of the plants from sap analysis (Esteves et al., 2021; Farneselli et al., 2014; Hochmuth, 1994) or optical sensors for fine-tuning of plant nutrition in both soilless and soil grown crops. Moreover, portable ISE sensors can be used for rapid sap and soil analysis with acceptable accuracy (Peña-Fleitas et al., 2021). Especially, in soil grown crops, the estimation of plant nutrient status will increase the accuracy and the efficiency of the fertigation. In SCS the DS composition corresponds to the RS and gives a better overview of the nutrition before the plants are affected by an imbalance in the RS (Sonneveld and Voogt, 2009; Voogt and Bar-Yosef, 2019). However, in soil grown crops, soil analysis is a slow procedure and rapid methods using water extraction do not take into consideration the available nutrients adsorbed in soil colloids which are easily available nutrient reserves playing a highly important role in nutrient supply to the crops. In this frame the estimation of nutrients levels in the plant tissues and soil solution will help in optimizing plant nutrition in soil grown crops and reducing the caused problems by excessive fertigation, such as N and P pollution of surface and underground waters.

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